

D6.1 Brand and Roadmap for Awareness Campaign

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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
COE	Centre of Excellence
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EuroHPC JU	EuroHPC Joint Undertaking
HPC	High Performance Computing
PU	Public
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This document is a deliverable of the HiDALGO2 project, funded by the European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking ('granting authority'), under the powers delegated by the European Commission ('European Commission'), under the Call "HORIZON-EuroHPC JU-JU-2021-COE-01 (CENTRES OF EXCELLENCE FOR HPC APPLICATIONS)", and proposal No 101093457.

It aims to provide the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP), part of Work Package 6 that will be implemented throughout the project's life, based on specific strategy and predefined steps. The D.C.P. will be drafted and delivered by Future Needs but all partners of the project will participate in the implementation of the communication and dissemination tasks.

The challenges addressed by this deliverable are to form a detailed communication strategy and action plan with the aim to consolidate project information and results into comprehensive and easy-to-read news outputs tailored for targeted audiences and stakeholders.

Readers will learn the communication and dissemination activities that will be performed during the project's lifetime, the specific tools for communication and dissemination, the target audiences and messages, the potential synergies, etc.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to elaborate in detail the specific steps of the communication and dissemination strategy in a complete plan. The plan includes communications guidelines, target audiences & messages, review procedure, the visual identity of the project, office templates, the press release publication plan, the website structure and components, the social media accounts to be used, a “toolkit” with all print marketing and promotion materials, the conferences participation, potential synergies, and, finally, the specific KPIs.

1.2 Relation to other project work

This document, “D.6.1. Brand and Roadmap for Awareness Campaign” (part of Work Package 6), is closely related with a number of other tasks and deliverables of the project.

Namely, we should mention:

- Task 2.3 “Dashboard and Service Offering” and related deliverable D2.3 “HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services”, that are both closely connected with tasks from WP6 on community building.
- Task 4.3 “Artificial Intelligence for Global Challenges” and related deliverable D4.2 “Advances in HPDA and AI for Global Challenges”. This task will support the pilot applications developed in WP5 and the supportive actions in WP6 using Artificial Intelligence (AI).
- Task 4.5 “Coupling Technologies” and related deliverable D4.1 “Data Management and Coupling Technologies”. This task’s activity goes across work packages WP2 to WP6, where infrastructure and development services are involved.
- WP5 – “Tackling Global Challenges”, is the heart of the project since it is where all the use case work takes place. The results of this entire WP will be a significant part of the project’s dissemination since it will be of great interest to external stakeholders.
- Task 6.3 “Expanding Competences by Trainings”
- Task 6.4 “Awareness Creation, Collaboration and Community Support”
- Task 6.5 “Project Branding, Dissemination and Communication” with related deliverable D6.2 “Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Activities”.

Finally, we should remind that the WP6 aims at promoting a sustainable operation of the Centre of Excellence, as well as at fostering communication and dissemination

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activities including training, workshops, collaboration with other projects and organisations, as well as demonstrating the HiDALGO2 results to the general public.

1.3 Structure of the document

This document is structured in **5** major chapters except the introduction (1).

Chapter 2 presents the dissemination, communication & clustering activities plan, explaining the division between communication and dissemination activities.

Chapter 3 presents the external communication plan elaborating the communication strategy, the messages, the audiences, specific guidelines and the material’s review procedure.

Chapter 4 presents the communication tools that are going to be used in the project, like the visual identity, the logotype, the office templates and the press releases publication.

Chapter 5 presents the online dissemination tools, like the website structure and components, the blog posts, the newsletter function, the social media activity and the communication on other platforms.

Chapter 6 presents the offline dissemination tools, like the printed promotional materials to be used in conferences and trainings, the publications and articles that will be presented during the project’s lifetime, and the potential collaborations and synergies with other projects, initiatives and bodies.

Chapter 7 describes briefly the conclusions.

In the **Annex 1**, the reader will find a table with all the KPIs and also there is a list with tables and a list with figures included in this document. **Annex 2** is to detail list of synergies.

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2. Dissemination, Communication & Clustering Activities Plan

There is a very close relationship between dissemination (spreading knowledge), communication (building awareness/promoting), and clustering activities (community building). HiDALGO2 will disseminate mainly its results such as data, models, patterns, use cases, scientific or technical papers, etc. HiDALGO2 aspires to have open communication channels with its stakeholders, allowing two-way communication and actively receiving feedback from the community when required.

2.1 Dissemination & Clustering activities

Dissemination is focused on transferring knowledge and depends on the kind of knowledge transferred to the target audience. To enhance the visibility of the project the following HiDALGO2 dissemination activities will be performed, such as participation and organization of clustering events, use of the online media (project website, newsletter, and social media), and meetings/trainings/workshops with relevant stakeholders. For example, in order to expand the community building that has already started in HiDALGO2, a dedicated EU Clustering event will be organized during the project's lifetime.

2.2 Communication activities

Communication activities are focused on conducting public engagement activities, i.e., events where specialists listen and interact with non-specialists, to ensure that research and innovation activities are made known to the professional as well as the society at large. Also, press releases of the project will be published in local and European media, uploaded on the project's website and spread on social media in order to communicate the results further. Additionally, articles related to the project will be published on European journals and on all partners' websites as well as on the project's website. Finally, the project is going to be presented in various conferences/seminars/events by the partners.

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3. External Dissemination and Communication Plan

This chapter describes the initial assumptions related to dissemination, communication & clustering activities of the HiDALGO2 project and presents the public website structures, while it also introduces additional tools such as social media, newsletter, press releases and printed materials.

The following communication plan will be continuously developed to ensure appropriate activities are performed to inform, engage, create awareness and promote information about the project, its aims, its funding source, its results, impacts and wider societal implications. The key objectives of such a plan are included below:

- Provide widespread visibility to the project and its outputs.
- Ensure that target audiences are convinced that due to European collaboration in HiDALGO2 more has been achieved than would otherwise be possible, as a result, the project has created measurable benefits to citizens and other stakeholders.
- Target key decision-makers who can support the implementation of the project.
- Demonstrate how the outcomes of HiDALGO2 are relevant to the lives of European citizens.
- Ensure that the results of HiDALGO2 influence policy makers and other decision-makers around pandemic preparedness and cross-border public health data sharing, to ensure long-term impact.

3.1 Dissemination and Communication Strategy

All project partners will perform communication and dissemination activities, but the content and the type will differ according to the nature of the partner and the targeted audience. The industrial partners will approach relevant standardization and regulatory bodies, industry sectors, as well as their distributors and client networks, while the academic and research partners will mainly focus on disseminating the project results to research institutes and universities as well as integrating them into international backgrounds. Such activities will prepare the creation of an active community capable of understanding the extent and importance of the project’s solutions, adopting them at later stages. HiDALGO2 will need to raise awareness of our target groups, namely: 1. Policy makers 2. Professionals in relevant technologies (research, academia, developers), 3. Technology providers, 4. Industry

The main goal of the HiDALGO2 dissemination strategy is to create and spread awareness of the project and its results to the broadest possible audience within the scientific and research community. To reach this goal HiDALGO2 will differentiate between two major strands of communication and dissemination: (i) the general

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promotion/communication activities, which will be focused mainly on the first months of the project, targeting the wide public audience (mainly through the communication channels of the project), and (ii) a set of more specific activities, dissemination activities, dedicated to the presentation of HiDALGO2 advances and outcomes to the scientific communities, academia, and industries (through dissemination means and clustering events). These dissemination activities will become more important as the project evolves and concrete results will become the focus of the dissemination plan/activities.

3.2 Dissemination messages

Dissemination and showcasing activities are of crucial importance for the project’s successful diffusion of knowledge, for raising awareness, and for attracting potential supporters, industries as well as scientific interest. The main objectives that will be fulfilled by the HiDALGO2 dissemination and showcasing actions are:

- To disseminate project outcomes to the scientific community.
- To disseminate and raise awareness of the project to relevant industries.
- To disseminate results and raise awareness of the project among the most important stakeholders (including ministries, administrations and other public bodies and decision-makers at EU and national levels).
- To foster inter-communication with other research projects and communities.
- To disseminate and communicate project innovations to the broader public and society.

3.3 Target audiences

HiDALGO2 communication, dissemination & clustering activities are executed by all the partners and differ regarding the nature of the partner as well as the means, content and target audience. The industrial partners will approach industry sectors and their distributors as well as client networks, whereas the academic and research partners will target relevant research institutes and universities. All partners will use their network to approach administrations and the public sector.

Overall, the target audience of the HiDALGO2 project is the following:

- Policy makers and public administrations: Policy makers in the fields of climate change and quality of life as well as crises preparedness and response will be the main target of HiDALGO2, being them at a regional, national, EU, and international level. Decision-makers have to be at the forefront and held accountable to ensure that measures are taken in the direction of minimising the

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risks of health problems and natural disasters affecting their area of responsibility.

- Professionals in relevant technologies (research, academia, developers): HPC and HPDA professionals/organisations are at the heart of the HiDALGO2 consortium and an important piece of the value chain in the battle against climate change, and thus one of the priority target audiences of the HiDALGO2 communication strategy. Training of the next generation of HPC and HPDA professionals in using new technologies will strengthen the environmental domain/sector. HiDALGO2 use case owners will experience first-hand the scenario of the use of HiDALGO2 tools during simulations as part of the demonstrators of HiDALGO2 and will be the torches who pass the light to their colleagues.
- Technology providers: To ensure that technology providers, potential users, and policy makers become aware of project results and how they can affect future platforms and services, the collaboration networks of partners and events targeting discussions between related stakeholders will be used. Several partners have open channels of discussion related to their markets and will use these to discuss project activities and solicit feedback. HiDALGO2 partners will make use of a set of dissemination activities, tools, channels that embrace “online and onsite engaging activities” to raise their interest and ensure their engagement in project activities. Deliverable D6.2 on the project communication and dissemination will provide a mapped ecosystem of key stakeholders to be engaged. Each partner will support FN in this process (from the translation of key messages into the national language, to sharing HiDALGO2 materials/ newsletter etc. within their corporate mailing lists). Under T6.5, partners will continue to map key stakeholders’ worth being engaged in project activities.
- The general public that is interested in HiDALGO2’s technological fields and advancements.
- All HiDALGO2 partners & collaborators: This document is addressed to the entire HiDALGO2 consortium and serves as initial documentation of the plans/strategies to be applied for efficiently performing communication, dissemination activities and clustering activities, partner-specific exploitation and standardisation activities and relevant collaborations in which HiDALGO2 partners, and stakeholders are involved and/or affected.

3.4 Communication guidelines

In the following paragraphs, we describe procedures and tools for producing, reviewing and publishing communication content in 8 steps.

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1st step: Communication material and deliverables content produced by FN will be placed in the collaborative environment suggested by the Coordinator, such as the common Drive platform already used in the project.

2nd step: Partners will be notified of the availability of materials online and be called to review them in a given timeframe for a concrete and reasonable amount of time (maximum 5 working days for communication material, 3 weeks for deliverables) through suggestions mode. This includes suggestions for authors on extra content, and on how to better structure and present the content. If the material is a deliverable, proof reading will be done by the Dissemination & Communication manager of the partner assigned as Internal Reviewer to the deliverable by the Coordinator.

3rd step: If partners find the timeframe unattainable, they can ask for an extension of the deadline. If an extension is possible without hindering project results, it will be granted.

4th step: Once all comments are inserted, FN will review and incorporate them, maintaining the right to deny a suggestion based on solid argumentation (e.g., EC rules, guidelines described in the communication plan).

5th step: The final version of the material will be reviewed by the Coordinator before proofreading.

6th step: FN will make the final version of the material available in the common Drive platform for a concrete and reasonable amount of time (maximum 5 working days for communication material, 2 weeks for deliverables) for all partners to proofread before publishing the material. We follow the “proofreading” definition of global publishing houses (e.g., Elsevier), meaning that proofreading focuses on correcting superficial errors in spelling, grammar, syntax, punctuation, and formatting. If the material is a deliverable, the proofreading will be done by the Dissemination & Communication manager of the partner assigned as Internal Reviewer to the deliverable by the Coordinator.

7th step: Proof-reading by Coordinator.

8th step: After the proof-reading stage, no further reviewing iterations are foreseen. FN will finalise and “seal” the material and the material will be published/ submitted to the EC.

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4. Communication tools

4.1 Visual identity / branding

The HiDALGO2 visual identity provides a clear identity and appearance. It comprises of the project logo and the following documents: press releases (published online), newsletters (online), project’s ppt presentation (online) and the project’s factsheet (a flyer on the website and in printed form).

4.2 HiDALGO2 logotype

It contains the project name and a signet/a graphic element that is the first letter “H”. The project’s logo has been finalised for all format requirements, and can be used in the communication templates, the first brochure and the poster.

The logo was released in one horizontal version in colour blue with a warm and expressive accent. The typography is based on a simple, one-piece element. The logo files are in png (transparent background), pdf, svg, jpeg, eps.

Figure 1. HiDALGO2 logo

4.2.1 Misuse of the logotype

It is preferred to use the logo on either a white or light grey background. The HiDALGO2 logo must be easily recognised, therefore it is encouraged to avoid cluttering the logo and use only the official version. All the components of the HiDALGO2 logo are in a fixed relationship and should never be altered, modified or reproduced in any way. Please avoid adding artistic effects.

- Do not erase or change in any way elements of the logotype
- Do not use outlines
- Do not use shadows
- Do not use 3D effects
- Do not change the colours
- Do not distort
- Do not rotate / mirror
- Do not change the typography

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Figure 2. Examples of logo misuse

Also, the logo used against background should not follow this rule because the elements of the logo are hidden against such a coloured or motived background:

Figure 3. Logo misuse against background

Instead, it should be used as follows:

Figure 4. Proper use of the logo

4.3 Project Repository

The Project Repository is maintained and hosted by PSNC, the project coordinator. The Project Repository is the main mean for communications and collaboration inside the project consortium. It includes all the project materials and all the project partners

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can access it and contribute to it. All versions of the project materials are uploaded to the Project Repository, work in progress, deliverables, promotional material, etc.

4.4 Office templates

The working templates are expected to be used in all communication related to the project, by all consortium members (all templates will be available on the shared Drive folder). The templates that are made for the project are: the deliverable template, a letter template, an empty template, a template for deliverables' peer review, a Telecommunications minutes template and a PowerPoint presentation template, a book of visual identification. It is possible to see some of these templates below:

Figure 5. The Letter of HiDALGO2

Figure 6. The presentation template PPT

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4.5 Press releases

HiDALGO2 will publish 2 press releases on its website, social media accounts, on Cordis Wire and on popular media outlets in all partners' countries. One press release will be issued at the project start and one for the middle term results promotion. All partners should publish the press release in the respective websites and social media accounts of their organisations. The main objective of press releases is to gain publicity and to raise public awareness.

The press release will be sent to the following media outlets, that are listed below by each partner's country.

Table 1. Mass Media source links

Channels per country and responsible partner	
International, English-speaking media & organisations/forums/news sites federations/observatories (with news sections)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CORDIS Wire https://cordis.europa.eu/news/en • HORIZON Magazine https://horizon-magazine.eu/ • EurActiv https://www.euractiv.com/pressrelease@euractiv.com • Euronews (Construction), https://www.euronews.com • Industry Europe mag, https://industryeurope.com • Eurocities, https://eurocities.eu/ • European Cluster Collaboration Platform, https://clustercollaboration.eu/ • Businesswire news site, https://www.businesswire.com • European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU), https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/contact_en • European Environmental Agency, https://www.eea.europa.eu/contact-us, Antti.Kaartinen@eea.europa.eu, Constant.Brand@eea.europa.eu • HPC Wire mag https://www.hpcwire.com/ • Frontiers in High Performance Computing Journal, https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/high-performance-computing, research.integrity@frontiersin.org • Inside HPC, https://insidehpc.com, news@insidehpc.com

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computer World, https://www.computerworld.com • Scientific Computing World, https://www.scientific-computing.com • ZDnet, https://www.zdnet.com/ • Channel Insider, the Next Platform, https://www.nextplatform.com/ • Computer Weekly, https://www.computerweekly.com/ • insideBigData, https://insidebigdata.com/
Cyprus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Φιλεnews, https://www.philenews.com/, mailbox@philelefttheros.com, philenews@philelefttheros.com • Sigma Live (tech), https://www.sigmalive.com/news/scitech/technology, news@sigmalive.com • Reporter, https://www.reporter.com.cy/, info@imhbusiness.com, reporter@imhbusiness.com • Alphanews live, https://www.alphanews.live/cyprus, portal@alphacyprus.com.cy • Cyprus Times, https://cyprustimes.com/, info@cyprustimes.com • Offsite news, https://www.offsite.com.cy/, info@offsite.com.cy • Η Καθημερινή Κύπρου, https://www.kathimerini.com.cy/gr/, info@kathimerini.com.cy • Ο Πολίτης, Error! Hyperlink reference not valid.https://politis.com.cy/ • Ant1 Κύπρου, Elli Kotzamani, e.kotzamani@antenna.com.cy • Διάλογος, https://dialogos.com.cy/ • CyprusNews, https://cyprusnews.eu/, info@cyprusnews.eu • ToThemaOnline, https://www.tothemaonline.com/, info@worldnewsmedia.net • Omegalive, https://omegalive.com.cy/, omegalive@cy.net, newsdpt@omegatv.com.cy

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brief, https://www.brief.com.cy/ https://www.brief.com.cy, info@brief.com.cy • InBusiness News (tech): https://inbusinessnews.reporter.com.cy/business/ict918, info@imhbusiness.com, events@imhbusiness.com • Cyprus Mail (tech): https://cyprus-mail.com/category/technology/, info@cyprus-mail.com • Cyl High Performance Computing Facility, https://hpcf.cyi.ac.cy/, hpc.support@cyi.ac.cy
Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C't, Heise online, https://www.heise.de/ • ChannelPartner, https://www.channelpartner.de/ • It-daily.net, IT Management, https://www.it-daily.net • DataCenter-Insider, https://www.datacenter-insider.de/
Hungary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Magyar Távirati Iroda, http://www.mti.hu/, bel@mti.hu, wild.petra@mtva.hu • Kisalföld, https://www.kisalfold.hu/, szerkesztoseg@kisalfold.hu, online@kisalfold.hu • Győr+, https://www.gyorplusz.hu/, media@gyorplusz.hu • Szabad Föld, https://szabadfold.hu/, szabadfold@szabadfold.hu • Forbes, https://forbes.hu/, szerk@forbes.hu • HVG Tech, https://hvg.hu/tudomany, balogh.csaba@hvg.hu • 24.hu Tech, https://24.hu/tech/, peter.birkas@24.hu • Műszaki Magazin, https://www.muszaki-magazin.hu, mzsolt@muszaki-magazin.hu • Portfólió, https://www.portfolio.hu, szandanyi@portfolio.hu • Gyártástrend, https://gyartastrend.hu/, hirek@gyartastrend.hu • TechWorld, https://techworld.hu/, info@techworld.hu

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New Technology, https://newtechnology.hu/, kapcsolat@newtechnology.hu, czako.miklos@newtechnology.hu • Technokrata, https://www.technokrata.hu/, hirek@technokrata.hu • Digital Hungary, https://www.digitalhungary.hu/, info@digitalhungary.hu • Tiszta Jövő, https://www.tisztajovo.hu/, szerveztoseg@tisztajovo.hu • Greendex, https://greendex.hu/, szerveztoseg@greendex.hu • Zöld Ipar Magazin, https://www.zipmagazin.hu/, info@zipmagazin.hu • ReCity, https://recity.hu/, szerveztoseg@recity.hu • Zöld Pálya, https://www.zoldpalya.hu/, info@zoldpalya.hu • Energiaoldal, https://energiaoldal.hu/, info@energiaoldal.hu
<p>Poland</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chip - https://www.chip.pl/ • Computer Science - https://journals.agh.edu.pl/csci/ • Computerworld - https://www.computerworld.pl/ • Delta - https://www.deltami.edu.pl/ • Domena - https://portal.pti.org.pl/domena/ • e-Informatica Software Engineering Journal - https://www.e-informatyka.pl/
<p>Spain</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EFE Agency - Environmental section https://efeverde.com/EFE Agency - Technology section https://efe.com/ciencia-y-tecnologia +34 91 3467245 • OSBO Digital Agency, Forestry and Environment https://osbodigital.es info@osbo.org.es +34 679 1904 87 • El Pais Newsletter / Retina (Technological newspaper supplement) Redaccion@elpais.es

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5. Online dissemination tools

5.1 Website

The project's website is connected to a domain and live at www.hidalgo2.eu. The content of the website is to be reviewed, approved and updated by all consortium members until the end of the project. It will include all the news about the activities of HiDALGO2 and related events that HiDALGO2 and its consortium members participate in. Consortium members participating in the above will provide the content (text and visual material like photographs, videos, diagrams, infographics etc.) to be uploaded on the website. Papers and other publications related to the project will be uploaded on the website, as well as newsletters, press releases. Social Media posts are linked to the website content and there is a twitter feed in the homepage, in order to increase the website's visibility and inform the community about the project and its activities. The website will be kept live 2 years after the project ends.

Strategies to increase traffic:

- social media campaigns linked to the website of the project.
- social media posts linked to the website of the project.

Figure 7. Front page of the website

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Table 2. Website’s structure

Audience	All - technical & non-technical audience (general public). In a broad sense the whole society – referring also as the general public.
Message	HiDALGO2 will share its concepts, results and achievements through its dedicated project website. The website will be the major tool of communication and promotion of the project.
Structure	<p>The website is divided into nine menu sections including: Home, About (the project), Use cases, Partners, Synergies, Trainings, News, Contact.</p> <p>Home: This is the main page of the website, which provides information regarding the project, its partners and options that trigger the attention of the end user prompting them to scrutinize and learn more about HiDALGO2. The homepage hosts several sections that easily navigate the visitors to the rest pages of the website for additional information.</p> <p>About: The “About” page incorporates an overview of the project, its main objectives and missions. Moreover, it provides information on the forthcoming use cases, trainings in the environmental areas (pilot domains) and in the topics of the effective use of HPC, HPDA and AI systems, workshops (as well as online stakeholder awareness workshops), hackathons, conferences, and community meetings.</p> <p>Use Cases: This page provides a detailed overview of the 5 use cases of the HiDALGO2 project: Urban Air Project (UAP), Urban Buildings (UB), Renewable Energy Sources, (RES), Wildfires (WF), Meteo-Hydrological Forecasting (MHF).</p> <p>Partners: The HiDALGO2 partners are proudly presented within the specific page along with their corresponding country of their origin and their specific role in the project.</p> <p>Synergies: In this part there is a list of projects that HiDALGO2 aims to be based upon and upscale, ensuring scalability and impact.</p> <p>Trainings: In this section, all online education materials on the innovations developed during the project’s progress will be available in English.</p> <p>News: This section is regularly updated with content including project events (including EU Clustering event of HiDALGO2 where the Sustainability Roadmap of the project will be presented), activities, news and other impactful dissemination material upon being published. The “News” page offers a preview of HiDALGO2 published news where visitors can scroll and click on a selected published article and be redirected to the respective page where the full article is made available. In this section there is a social media news feed, all the newsletters and press releases and finally the brochure (project factsheet) of the project. This section also contains blog posts and downloads.</p>

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Contact: The contact form is an integral part of the website and serves as a bidirectional means of interaction among the stakeholders of the project and the project team. In this section emerging issues and queries are explicated and, upon receipt, they are addressed accordingly by the HiDALGO2 administration team. Furthermore, clickable icons of the HiDALGO2 social media channels exist at the header and the footer of the home page through which users can easily visit the respective channels.

5.2 Blog posts

One blog post every month (starting from Month 2) will be published on the website. All partners contribute to this task following a rotation plan that can be found in the shared drive folder of the project.

5.3 Newsletters

The HiDALGO2 newsletter is published three times per year of the project and shared with the public via the project’s social media accounts and website. Each newly issued newsletter is uploaded to the official website, prompting the users to read it online or download it. Moreover, the HiDALGO2 social media accounts will actively promote each issue by providing a direct link to the official website’s respective page. KPIs: 300 individuals/ organisations signed up to receive newsletters by M24 and at least 600 total by M48.

Table 3. Newsletter publication plan

Newsletter Issue	Release Month	Content Submission by
1 st	M4 (April 2023)	31.03.23
2 nd	M9 (September 2023)	31.08.23
3 rd	M12 (December 2023)	30.11.23
4 th	M16 (April 2024)	31.03.24
5 th	M21 (September 2024)	31.08.24
6 th	M24 (December 2024)	30.11.24
7 th	M28 (April 2025)	31.03.24
8 th	M33 (September 2025)	31.08.25

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9 th	M36 (December 2025)	30.11.25
10 th	M40 (April 2026)	31.03.26
11 th	M45 (September 2026)	31.08.26
12 th	M48 (December 2026)	30.11.26

5.4 Social Media

HiDALGO2 is present in key popular social media networks. In specific, the following HiDALGO2 social media accounts are open and have been actively used since February 2023 in Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and Youtube. Their access links are the following:

- Twitter: @HiDALGO2_EU, https://twitter.com/HiDALGO2_EU
- LinkedIn: HiDALGO2 Project, <https://www.linkedin.com/company/HiDALGO2/>
- YouTube: @HiDALGO2, <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCajli2XMTsQRDMKcvgvvoaAg>
- Facebook: [Hidalgo2 EU Project](https://www.facebook.com/EU.Project.HiDALGO), <https://www.facebook.com/EU.Project.HiDALGO>

HiDALGO2 social media posts are oriented towards promoting the project’s news as well as the dissemination activities in which the partners participate. Dissemination activities will cover a wide spectrum of events, publications, presentations, workshops, training, collaboration with other projects and organisations, as well as demonstrating the HiDALGO2 results to the general public. All this will be communicated through the website and social media.

Specifically, the social media posts cover the following activities:

- News and updates on the HiDALGO2 activities and progression of project tasks and deliverables
- Papers and presentations originating from workshops, conferences, journals etc.
- Project use cases
- Publications in articles, online sources, newspapers
- Upcoming events prompting stakeholders for papers and events participation
- Videos and photos
- Partners HiDALGO2 related activities and achievements
- Newsletter issues
- Articles on related topics (supercomputing, exascale, big data analysis, AI, etc)

In addition, all communicative HiDALGO2 social media channels can be found in the header and the footer of the project’s official website. Each of those social media icons,

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when clicked, may redirect the users to the respective HiDALGO2 social media channel. Moreover, the social media channels, amongst others, have an important role in promoting the HiDALGO2 newsletter.

In HiDALGO2, all partners in rotation will be responsible for the social media posting and management. During their responsibility period, each partner will create new content. The partners are also responsible for identifying influencers and sharing their details with the social media Leader to follow. Accounts which do not qualify as influencers but are still a worthy source of information, should not be followed but rather added to the respective Twitter lists.

Number of posts:

- 9 tweets per week (2 HiDALGO2 project promotion tweets, 7 re-tweets)
- LinkedIn/Facebook posts per week (1 HiDALGO2 project promotion post, 2 general relevant content posts)

Social media KPIs: Over 1000 Twitter followers, over 1500 LinkedIn followers, over 5000+ likes on Twitter and LinkedIn. At least 5 other projects involved in various online campaigns.

See below the rotation plan that the project will follow during the whole period of the project:

Table 4. Rotation plan

Partner	Weeks to be responsible for social media	
PSNC	27/2/2022	3/3/2023
	8/5/2023	14/5/2023
	3/7/2023	9/7/2023
	28/8/2023	3/9/2023
	23/10/2023	29/10/2023
	1/1/2024	7/1/2024
	26/2/2024	3/3/2024
	6/5/2024	12/5/2024
	1/7/2024	7/7/2024
	26/8/2024	1/9/2024
	21/10/2024	27/10/2024
	16/12/2024	22/12/2024
	24/2/2025	2/3/2025
	21/4/2025	27/4/2025
	16/6/2025	22/6/2025
11/8/2025	17/8/2025	
6/10/2025	12/10/2025	
1/12/2025	7/12/2025	

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	26/1/2026	1/2/2026
	23/3/2026	29/3/2026
	18/5/2026	24/5/2026
	13/7/2025	19/7/2025
	7/9/2026	13/9/2026
	2/11/2026	8/11/2026
USTUTT	20/3/2023	26/3/2023
	15/5/2023	21/5/2023
	10/7/2023	16/7/2023
	4/9/2023	10/9/2023
	30/10/2023	5/11/2023
	8/1/2024	14/1/2024
	4/3/2024	10/3/2024
	13/5/2024	19/5/2024
	8/7/2024	14/7/2024
	2/9/2024	8/9/2024
	28/10/2024	3/11/2024
	6/1/2025	12/1/2025
	3/3/2025	9/3/2025
	28/4/2025	4/5/2025
	23/6/2025	29/6/2025
	18/8/2025	24/8/2025
	13/10/2025	19/10/2025
	8/12/2025	14/12/2025
	2/2/2026	8/2/2026
	30/3/2026	5/4/2026
	25/5/2026	31/5/2026
	20/7/2025	26/7/2025
	14/9/2026	20/9/2026
ATOS	13/3/2023	19/3/2023
	22/5/2023	28/5/2023
	17/7/2023	23/7/2023
	11/9/2023	17/9/2023
	6/11/2023	12/11/2023
	15/1/2024	21/1/2024
	11/3/2024	17/3/2024
	20/5/2024	26/5/2024
	15/7/2024	21/7/2024
	9/9/2024	15/9/2024
	4/11/2024	10/11/2024
	13/1/2025	19/1/2025
	10/3/2025	16/3/2025
5/5/2025	11/5/2025	

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	25/8/2025	31/8/2025
	20/10/2025	26/10/2025
	15/12/2025	21/12/2025
	9/2/2026	15/2/2026
	6/4/2026	12/4/2026
	1/6/2025	7/6/2025
	27/7/2025	2/8/2026
	21/9/2026	27/9/2026
	16/11/2026	22/11/2026
SZE	6/3/2023	12/3/2023
	29/5/2023	4/6/2023
	24/7/2023	30/7/2023
	18/9/2023	24/9/2023
	13/11/2023	19/11/2023
	22/1/2024	28/1/2024
	18/3/2024	24/3/2024
	18/3/2024	24/3/2024
	22/7/2024	28/7/2024
	16/9/2024	22/9/2024
	11/11/2024	17/11/2024
	20/1/2025	26/1/2025
	17/3/2025	23/3/2025
	12/5/2025	18/5/2025
	7/7/2025	13/7/2025
	1/9/2025	7/9/2025
	27/10/2025	2/11/2025
22/12/2025	28/12/2025	
16/2/2026	22/2/2026	
13/4/2026	19/4/2026	
8/6/2025	14/6/2025	
3/8/2026	9/8/2026	
28/9/2026	4/10/2026	
23/11/2026	29/11/2026	
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	5/6/2023	11/6/2023
	31/7/2023	6/8/2023
	25/9/2023	1/10/2023
	20/11/2023	26/11/2023
	29/1/2024	4/2/2024
	1/4/2024	7/4/2024
	3/6/2024	9/6/2024
29/7/2024	4/8/2024	

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	18/11/2024	24/11/2024
	27/11/2025	2/2/2025
	24/3/2025	30/3/2025
	19/5/2025	25/5/2025
	14/7/2025	20/7/2025
	8/9/2025	14/9/2025
	3/11/2025	9/11/2025
	29/12/2026	4/1/2026
	23/2/2026	1/3/2026
	20/4/2026	26/4/2026
	15/6/2025	21/6/2025
	10/8/2026	16/8/2026
	5/10/2026	11/10/2026
	30/11/2026	6/12/2026
CEMOSIS	17/4/2023	23/4/2023
	12/6/2023	18/6/2023
	7/8/2023	13/8/2023
	2/10/2023	8/10/2023
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	8/4/2024	14/4/2024
	10/6/2024	16/6/2024
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22/6/2026	28/6/2026	
17/8/2026	23/8/2026	
12/10/2026	18/10/2026	
7/12/2026	13/12/2026	
ICCS	24/4/2023	30/4/2023
	19/6/2023	25/6/2023
	14/8/2023	20/8/2023
	9/10/2023	15/10/2023

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	12/2/2024	18/2/2024
	15/4/2024	21/4/2024
	17/6/2024	23/6/2024
	12/8/2024	18/8/2024
	7/10/2024	13/10/2024
	2/12/2024	8/12/2024
	10/2/2025	16/2/2025
	7/4/2025	13/4/2025
	2/6/2025	8/6/2025
	28/7/2025	3/8/2025
	22/9/2025	28/9/2025
	17/11/2025	23/11/2025
	12/1/2026	18/1/2026
	9/3/2026	15/3/2026
	4/5/2026	10/5/2026
	29/6/2026	5/7/2026
	24/8/2026	30/8/2026
	19/10/2026	25/10/2026
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	16/10/2023	22/10/2023
	11/12/2023	17/12/2023
	18/12/2023	24/12/2023
	25/12/2023	31/12/2023
	19/2/2024	25/2/2024
	22/4/2024	28/4/2024
	29/4/2024	5/5/2024
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	19/8/2024	25/8/2024
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	30/12/2024	5/1/2025
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	14/4/2025	20/4/2025
9/6/2025	15/6/2025	
4/8/2025	10/8/2025	
29/9/2025	5/10/2025	
24/11/2025	30/11/2025	

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	16/3/2026	22/3/2026
	11/5/2026	17/5/2026
	6/7/2026	12/7/2026
	31/8/2026	6/9/2026
	26/10/2026	1/11/2026
	14/12/2026	20/12/2026
	21/12/2026	27/12/2026

5.4.1 HiDALGO2 social media accounts analytically

5.4.1.1 Twitter

Twitter will be one of the main communication channels of the project. It will be mainly used to post latest updates and also post “in-real time” during project’s events and participation to activities.

Figure 8. Twitter account

Table 5. Posting on Twitter

Audience	All - technical & non-technical audience (general public). In a broad sense the whole society – referring also as the general public.
Message	As a result of the strategy followed so far at all social media channels is the fast accumulation of followers. From the specific profile page, a user can be redirected to the HiDALGO2’s posts made over Twitter, access follower’s posts, read project identity and info, and also redirected to HiDALGO2’s official website when clicking the link residing below the project’s bio.

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Post objectives	HiDALGO2 project will continuously communicate via its social media channels its activities and achievements. In addition, the project will take the opportunity to reshare our partners' activities.
Guidelines	Text of up to 280 characters . This excludes media attachments (photos, images, videos, etc.) and quoted tweets (displaying tweet(s) of someone else within your own) but includes links (a URL is always altered to 23 characters).

5.4.1.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is the second communication channel the project will use to reach out to its audience. Due to the media's nature, it will be used mostly to reach out to professionals and academia.

Figure 9. LinkedIn account

Table 6. Posting on LinkedIn

Audience	All - technical & non-technical audience (general public). As the project is quite 'professional-oriented', it also targets technicians. In a broader sense the whole society is benefited from the project – referring also as the general public.
Message	There is a short bio of the project including its objectives and quantitative details. The audience can easily check the latest project posts and communicate directly with the HiDALGO2 team in case of any queries.

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Post objectives	HiDALGO2 project will continuously communicate via its social media channels its activities and achievements. In addition, the project will take the opportunity to reshare our partners' activities.
Guidelines	Text (no character limit), photos, GIFs, videos, links, etc.

5.4.1.3 Facebook

Facebook is another communication channel that the project will use. Even though it is not one of the main communication channels, the project will use it to post updates and reach to different user groups, potentially interested in the project activities or results.

Figure 10. Facebook account

Table 7. Posting on Facebook

Audience	All - technical & non-technical audience (general public). In a broad sense the whole society – referring also as the general public.
Message	There is a short bio of the project including its objectives and quantitative details. The audience can easily check the latest project posts and communicate directly with the HiDALGO2 team in case of any queries.
Post objectives	HiDALGO2 project will continuously communicate via its social media channels its activities and achievements. In addition, the project will take the opportunity to reshare our partners' activities.
Guidelines	Text (no character limit), photos, GIFs, videos, links, etc.

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5.4.1.4 YouTube

YouTube will be used to post project videos ensuring that they reach interested parties.

Figure 11. YouTube account

Table 8. Posting on YouTube

Audience	All - technical & non-technical audience (general public). In a broad sense the whole society – referring also as the general public.
Message	There is a short bio of the project including its objectives and quantitative details. The audience can easily check the latest project videos and communicate directly with the HiDALGO2 team in case of any queries.
Videos objectives	HiDALGO2 project will continuously communicate via its social media channels its activities and achievements. In addition, we will take the opportunity to reshare our partners' activities. It will be especially useful for promoting demos and use cases.
Guidelines	<p>Description text (5000-character limit) is better when it includes keywords that can help viewers find your videos more easily through search. You can give an overview of your video and place keywords in the beginning of the description.</p> <p>Example keywords: exascale, supercomputing, AI, big data, High Performance Computing.</p> <p>Supported video file formats: .MOV, .MPEG-1, .MPEG-2, .MPEG4, .MP4, .MPG, .AVI, .WMV, .MPEGPS, .FLV, 3GPP, WebM, DNxHR, ProRes, CineForm, HEVC (h265)</p>

5.5 Partners' websites

HiDALGO2 partners involved in various communities at national and international level will promote the project concept and use cases through these communities and through their institutions/companies.

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Table 9. Partners titles and websites

1. INSTYTUT CHEMII BIOORGANICZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK (PCNS), www.psnc.pl	PL Coordinator
2. HIGH- PERFORMANCE COMPUTING CENTER STUTTGART (HLRS), https://www.hlrs.de	DE
3. ATOS SPAIN SA, www.atos.net	ES
4. SZECHENYI ISTVAN EGYETEM (SZE), http://uni.sze.hu	HU
5. METEOGRID SL (MTG), http://www.meteogrid.com	ES
6. CEMOSIS (UNIVERSITE DE STRASBOURG- UNISTRA, http://www.unistra.fr	FR
7. INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS (ICCS), www.iccs.gr	EL
8. FUTURE NEEDS MANAGEMENT CONSULTING LTD (FN), http://futureneeds.eu/	CY

5.6 Communication on other platforms

- HiDALGO2 will collaborate with CORDIS. The project will constantly be in communication with this page in order to provide updates about the progress of HiDALGO2 and promote our achievements. Press releases of the project will also be published there.
- HiDALGO2 will also submit the projects' use cases on the **EOSC Portal Catalogue & Marketplace** (<https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-in-practice/open-call>). Facilitating access to HiDALGO2 services from the level of **EOSC Portal Catalogue & Marketplace** will be another step towards federalization of European resources and unification of access for a wider group of recipients.
- Reports and only public deliverables of HiDALGO2 can be published in the Research Gate platform, in the "Experiment Findings" section (<https://www.researchgate.net/>).

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5.7 ResearchGate

HiDALGO2 will use ResearchGate is a social networking platform designed specifically for researchers and scientists. It will serve as an additional platform for collaboration, knowledge sharing, and dissemination of research findings. Even though projects have been discontinued in ResearchGate, project researchers will make use of its large network and recognisability in order to share their publications derived from the HiDALGO2 work, including journal articles, conference papers, book chapters, and preprints. This approach will allow others to access and read the project work, potentially leading to further collaborations or even extend project's results.

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6. Offline dissemination tools

6.1 Printed promotional material

HiDALGO2 will create respective brochure and posters serving as promotional material which will include key factors of the project.

Figure 12. The first HiDALGO2 poster

Prior to any publication in peer-reviewed journals, conference proceedings, etc. partners need to inform about their plans

1. the WP Leader, about the production of a paper related to their WP
2. the Dissemination WP Leader
3. and the project Coordinator.

The WP Leader should make a first assessment in terms of the scientific/technological relevance of the paper to the project. Simultaneously, the Dissemination WP leader together with the Coordinator will also assess the relevance of the paper in line with the comments from PO/reviewers, as Research Innovation Action. After this assessment, information about approval for publication will be provided to the authors. Authors need to submit the draft-publication at least 15 days before submitting the camera-ready version for publication to the WP leader.

This procedure allows sufficient time for the draft to be assessed and approved for publication by the WP Leader, Dissemination WP leader and Coordinator, representing the interests of all partners and that of the European Commission to raise any objections, before the material is published. In other words, no material should be submitted for publication (in a journal or proceedings), without allowing sufficient time for withdrawal in the event of objections being raised. Publications should include a legal notice (to be provided).

All papers approved for publication under the frame of HiDALGO2 project should include the proper acknowledgement to the project.

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In case that aforementioned procedure is not followed, neither expenses nor effort associated with the production of paper under discussion will be justified.

6.2 Specific printed material for events

The printed or online visual material necessary for the official project events like the EU Clustering event (programme, badges etc.) is decided and created by the organiser(s). It is advised to consult with the Dissemination manager on the templates and the (English) content of the material created, before finalising them.

6.3 Publications

HiDALGO2 project will coordinate publications and will contribute in open access journals. An indicative but not exhaustive list of examples follow: Environmental Science & Policy, [Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulations](#) (JASSS), Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing (JPDC), IEEE Transactions on Big Data, Forest Policy and Economics journal.

6.4 Articles

About the peer-reviewed papers & popular science articles: There will be submission and acceptance for publication of 25 articles, and a total of 10 articles on third party websites. The third party media that the articles will be published will be selected based on their content and by paying great attention to the future exploitation of the project. The articles will acknowledge the EU contribution to the project.

6.5 Conferences/ external events/workshops

The plan will include a list of targeted external events, and conferences. Initially, the consortium has identified some of them, as we consider them relevant (see table below). In the shared drive of the project, there is a file with a list of proposed events and conferences, where all partners can add their information.

Consortium members will present there (conferences, info days, business days, forums, hackathlons), the HiDALGO2 project and its objectives, missions, educational material, results of the use cases, etc., in order to disseminate even further the project. Photos of the events with HiDALGO2 brochure/poster/presentation, etc. have to be sent to Future Needs for use at the social media and the website (news section).

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KPIs: Consortium partners will attend at **least 30 conferences, trade shows, workshops, and networking activities** with pertinent EU/national projects in order to maximise the dissemination and impact of the project.

Table 10. External Conferences/ Events

Where	<p>Indicatively mentioned:</p> <p><u>Conferences</u>: International Conference on Computational Science (ICCS); International Conference on High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis (SC); International Conference on Air Quality Science and Application; International Conference on Supercomputing (ICS); International Conference on Advances in Forest Fire Management.</p> <p><u>Events</u>: EuroHPC Summit Week; TERATEC; European Data Forum; International Workshop on Runtime and Operating Systems for Supercomputers (ROSS); INSPIRE Hackathons.</p>
Message	<p>Objectives for the conferences are to disseminate the project’s results and outputs. The partners are advised to align when more than one consortium organisation is participating in an event or conference, in order to maximise the benefits of the activity for the project.</p>

How the project will monitor the progress:

Partners should inform the Dissemination WP leader about any planned participation at an event. Before the event, as soon as partners are considering participating in an event, partners should inform the Dissemination WP leader on:

- Whether they plan to participate using their own resources or HiDALGO2’s budget and in the latter case what the estimated required budget is.
- The type of participation at the event: i) Merely visitor, networking & distribution of brochures; ii) Stand at the exhibition area; iii) Organization of a conference; iv) Participation in a conference with a presentation; v) Participation in a conference with paper submission (specify if there is also an oral presentation); vi) Organization of a workshop at a conference; vii) Participation in a workshop the with presentation; viii) other (please, specify).
- Expected KPIs to be achieved from such participation: i) Estimated nr. of participants. ii) Promotional material (brochures/roll-up/posters) to be distributed at the event. iii) Any planned or pre scheduled bilateral meetings/speed dating), iv) other.

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The Dissemination WP Leader together with the Coordinator will assess if the envisaged participation at an event using HiDALGO2’s budget is justifiable and acceptable.

After the event, partners should inform the dissemination WP leader regarding:

- Actual costs associated with the participation.
- Actual KPIs from the participation: i) Nr. of people receiving info about HiDALGO2 ii) Nr. of brochures/ promotional material distributed; iii) Nr. of contacts made (+ contact details) i.e., Contacts interested in a demo, potential customers, contacts interested in a collaboration, other iv) Nr. collaborations i.e. contacts for planned collaborations - EU project interested in co-development, companies interested in exploitation)
- Photos of the event with HiDALGO2’s brochure/poster/presentation, etc.

If the aforementioned procedure is not followed, neither travel expenses nor effort associated with the event under discussion will be justified.

6.6 Presentations

In their project presentations, partners should avoid infringement of the rights of other HiDALGO2 partners by, for example, revealing sensitive or confidential information. If in doubt, check with the Coordinator or the partners concerned. In each presentation referring to the project, acknowledgement of the support of the European Community must be included. You must also include a disclaimer that the presentation reflects only the author’s views/opinions and that the Community accepts no liability as stated above.

Project specific presentations need to be available in the MS PowerPoint format, before the presentation is delivered. This is mandatory to allow the uptake of the presentation contents (as far as it does not affect any IPR regulations) by other project stakeholders. If the presentations are available for publishing, they must be shared in a pdf format.

Nonetheless, it is requested that partners, who want to make use of content produced by other partners, need their agreement in advance.

Copyright of the HiDALGO2 styles and templates belongs jointly to all project partners who are free to use those templates and assert their copyright over what they derive from those templates. Any partner developing a project-related presentation may then assert its copyright over that presentation with a simple copyright statement referencing the legal entity holding the copyright (e.g., Copyright © 2023 Future Needs). Please be advised that the HiDALGO2 Consortium does not constitute a legal entity and so cannot assert copyright, although individual members can, of course, assert copyright. If you wish to share the copyright of a presentation with the other members of the HiDALGO2 Consortium, the following is an acceptable form, “Copyright ©2023 Future Needs and

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other members of the HiDALGO2 Consortium.” Note that “Copyright ©2023 Future Needs” means that slides cannot be used by other parties without the permission of Future Needs, whereas the latter form gives members of the HiDALGO2 Consortium permission to use and modify those slides as they wish.

Bearing in mind the above-mentioned implications, the project partners are free to use the form they wish.

6.7 First HiDALGO2 leaflet

The first leaflet produced for promoting HiDALGO2 was designed and first distributed in the ISC 2023 in May 2023. The leaflet will be used as printed hand-out dissemination material in future events as well.

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Figure 13: First HiDALGO2 leaflet

6.8 Collaborations/ Synergies

HiDALGO2 intends to actively cooperate with other **Centres of Excellence (CoEs)** (as it happened previously in HiDALGO in order to develop a synergy effect. A relationship with **CASTIEL2** will be established towards promoting project competences and services to industrial users. Another level of cooperation is **EOSC**. Facilitating access to HiDALGO2 services from the level of "**EOSC Portal Catalog & Marketplace**" will be another step towards the federalization of European resources and unification of access for a wider group of recipients.

HiDALGO2 is highly ambitious and in order to achieve its maximum potential it is linked with various actions with collaboration agreements, specifically the following:

- Plasma Exascale-Performance Simulations CoE - Pushing flagship plasma simulations codes to tackle exascale-enabled Grand Challenges via performance optimisation and codesign, Plasma-PEPSC, 101093261, funded by EuroHPC JU [1]
- BioExcel Centre of Excellence for Computational Biomolecular Research, BioExcel-3, 101093290, funded by EuroHPC JU [2]
- Center of Excellence for Exascale CFD, CEEC, 101093393, funded by EuroHPC JU [3]

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- Coordination and Support for National Competence Centres and Centres of Excellence on a European Level Phase 2, CASTIEL 2, 101102047, funded by EuroHPC JU
- Centre of Excellence in exascale-oriented application co-design and delivery for multiscale simulations, MultiXscale, 101093169, funded by EuroHPC JU [4]
- Center of Excellence for Exascale in Solid Earth - Second Phase, ChEESE-2P, 101093038, funded by EuroHPC JU [5]
- Center of excellence for weather and climate phase 3, ESiWACE3, 101093054, funded by EuroHPC JU [6]
- European Centre of Excellence for Engineering Applications on HPC and associated technologies, EXCELLERAT P2, 101092621, funded by EuroHPC JU [7]
- Materials design at the eXascale, MaX, 101093374, funded by EuroHPC JU [8]
- Scalable Parallel and distributed Astrophysical Codes for Exascale, SPACE, 101093441, funded by EuroHPC JU [9]

In the project's repository, there is a file with a list of proposed synergies, projects, bodies, networks, etc, where each partner can add their relevant information. This is a live document, frequently updated, but a part of the current version during the date of the deliverable is presented in Annex 2. The complete list is not part of this deliverable, hence the parts presented are not the complete work.

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7. Conclusions

The challenges posed in this deliverable are the utmost reach and impact of the project outcomes to the widest possible audiences, key stakeholders and specialised bodies. All partners have to contribute to this cause with their weekly input for social media and the website of the project as well as collaborating during the organisation of the project's participation in events and conferences. The main results of this document will provide input for other important steps of the project such as the community building, the outreach to specialised audiences, the take up of HiDALGO2's technologies from the local communities, etc. The next steps in this strategy analysed here in this document will mainly concern the involvement of the project to important events such as the ISC2023 Conference, the HiPEAC 2024 and the CASTIEL2 CoEs upcoming meetings.

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References

- [1] Plasma-PEPSC - <https://plasma-pepsc.eu/>
- [2] BioExcel - <https://bioexcel.eu/>
- [3] CEEC - Center of Excellence for Exascale CFD - https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/research-innovation-0/our-projects/ceec-center-excellence-exascale-cfd_en
- [4] MultiXscale - <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093169>
- [5] ChEESA-2P - <https://cheese2.eu/>
- [6] ESIWACE3 - <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093054/pl>
- [7] EXCELLERAT P2 - <https://www.excellerat.eu/>
- [8] MaX - <http://www.max-centre.eu/>
- [9] SPACE - <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093441>

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Annex 1 – Communication and dissemination KPIs

Below, the basic communication and dissemination KPIs that relate to all partners' involvement in the dissemination task are presented and in order to reach them all partners' contribution is needed. It is possible to see the project's aims related to: websites visitors, social media followers, press releases number of publications, projects papers' number, project's flyer's number of publications/distribution, participation in conferences, advisory board members participation, external associations' engagement, etc.

Every month, Future Needs organises & leads a meeting dedicated to the activities of WP6 where all partners align on their contribution to the achievement of the KPIs listed below. Conclusions and agreed actions are included in the meeting minutes uploaded in the project's shared folders.

Instrument	Targeted stakeholder	KPIs
Website	All stakeholders	Project website (launch in M4 with continuous updates), at least 8,000 unique visits by M48.
Visual Identity	All Stakeholders	Project logo has been finalised for all format requirements therefore development of communication templates (M02), first brochure and poster (M06).
Press releases	Citizens, NGOs, Media, public authorities	2 press releases which are take-up by CORDIS Wire and by popular media outlets in all project countries
Newsletters	Policy-makers, media, researchers, NGOs, public authorities	Publication three times a year. 300 individuals/organisations signed up to receive newsletters by M24 and at least 600 in total by M48.
Project factsheet	All stakeholders	Publication of flyer on website with 250 downloads. 1500 copies distributed at third-party events attended. At least one factsheet displayed in a public organisation or local authority visited by citizens and sector professionals.
Presentations at third-party events	Policy makers, Researchers, NGOs	Consortium partners will attend at least 30 conferences, trade shows, workshops, and networking activities with pertinent EU/national projects.
Peer-reviewed papers & popular science articles	Researchers & Media	Submission and acceptance for publication of 25 articles, a blog post every month (starting from Month 2) on the website and a total of 10 articles on third party websites
Social Media	Planners, Professionals, general public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Over 1000 Twitter followers, over 1500 LinkedIn followers. •Over 5000+ likes on Twitter and LinkedIn. At least 5 other projects involved in various online campaigns. •Over 30 followers in ResearchGate and more than 500 reads.
HiDALGO2 Workshops & Clustering Event	All stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •At least 5 public authorities and at least 10 other stakeholders from at least 6 different countries (not limited to the EU) are included in an advisory board. •Develop a Community on regional levels: at least 10 stakeholders in each partner country engaged in project activities; •At least 60 persons will attend the Clustering Event.

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Annex 2 – List of Synergies

A	B	C	D	E
Event	When	Where	Event Link	HIDALGO Role
SIAM Conference 2023	26 Feb - 3 March 2023	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	https://www.siam.org/conferences/cm/conference/cse23	Organize a mini-symposium, present lectures, joint event with EXCELLERAT
EuroHPC Summit 2023	20 - 23 March 2023	Gothenburg, Sweden	https://www.eurohpcsummit.eu/	Discussion panel, Present Poster
International Conference on Supercomputing (ICS) 2023	21 - 25 May 2023	Hamburg, Germany	https://www.ics-hpc.com/	Presence in EuroHPC Booth 1h project presentation Leaflets distributions Share Graphical Board with Cheese-2P
International Conference on Computational Science (ICCS)				

A	B
Synergy (Project, Community etc.)	Synergy website
EXCELLERAT CoE , European Centre of Excellence for Engineering Applications	https://www.excellerat.eu/
HIPEAC , Network driving European computing research and industry forward from #edge to #cloud to #IoT. Funded by the #EU	https://www.hipeac.net/
CASTIEL project , The Coordination and Support Action for National Competence Centres on a European level, https://www.eurocc-access.eu/	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/951740
CYENS Centre of Excellence , Sharing highlights and technology breakthroughs from the CYENS research groups as well as the local scientific community, Cyprus	https://www.cyens.org.cy/en-gb/
Dialogik gGmbH Institute	https://www.dialogik-expert.de/en/projects/hidalgo
ESIWACE project	https://www.esiwace.eu/
EuroCC project , EuroCC will bring together expertise to set up a network of National Competence Centres in HPC across Europe in 33 member and associated states.	https://www.eurocc-access.eu/
AI4DI project , AI4DI- Artificial Intelligence for Digitising Industry. This project receives funding from ECSEL JU and national funding agencies under grant agreement no826060	https://ai4di.eu/
Cineca project , Consortium made up of 40 Italian universities w/70 research Institutions & Italian Ministries of Education and Universities. HPC & IT for Higher Education	https://www.cineca.it/
EUPEX Pilot project , EUropean Pilot for EXascale, a @EuroHPC_JU	

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